

MARKET PRINCIPLES OF PARTNERSHIP IN IMPLEMENTING THE DUAL MODEL IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Dual training is considered to be a current and completely logical model of the interaction of educational organizations with other subjects of market relations, additional license requirements for the licensee in the implementation of educational activities expressed opinions about. It is analyzed that the dual model ensures the integration of the modern business community into the breadth of education on an equal basis.*

Keywords: *dual education, market relations, model, licensee, dual model, modern business community, integration, free formation of prices, self-management of economic activity, free choice of types and forms of activity.*

In the introduction to this article, the modern world economic community is actively searching for and implementing the most advanced technological processes in all sectors. World manufacturers are investing funds comparable to the budgets of small African countries in technological upgrading of their production. And these investments are absolutely justified, because in the future, from the introduction of new technologies, the manufacturer will confidently expand and monopolize sales markets, increase the volume of product production, reduce its cost, reduce employees, optimize logistics processes and increase its profit many times, thereby increasing its will cover their investments in new technologies. This process is the locomotive of the development of the entire economic model, which includes the producers of goods, their partners who perform auxiliary production functions and, of course, forms a new line of competences. It should be noted that the change of abilities does not only concern the entire production environment that produces and sells a new product, but also forms new consumer abilities in the participants of the consumer market.

Considering the theoretical aspects of the article, the labor market immediately reacts to the needs of producers of goods, provides vacancies (vacancies) conditioned by a wide package of requirements for its participants, and mobilizes the professional education system to radically improve the areas to be implemented. Unfortunately, for a number of reasons, educational organizations do not touch the content of the professional training courses implemented by higher education institutions, namely, the content of the practical-oriented educational process, emphasizing results, which in a certain sense makes educational organizations in accordance with the rapidly changing requirements for the training of specialists. and puts him in a difficult enough situation that he cannot react quickly. It is necessary to note that a number of educational organizations are lagging behind in terms of technological equipment, the result of this lagging can be seen in their inability to meet the demand for personnel.

Dual training is considered to be a relevant and fully logical model of interaction of educational organizations with other subjects of market relations. In the former Soviet Union, as well as the European experience, the principles and models of dual education, which are lost today, were actively and successfully used at various stages of the state's establishment. These principles and models included the interaction of educational organizations with production. Cooperation within the framework of belonging to one network has been particularly successful. The importance of the old-new model was the integration of the future specialist into the professional environment, which is called specialization. Adapting it to the role of an employee of an enterprise or organization in the social plan is no less important than professional adaptation.

At the moment, while paying attention to the practical aspects of the article, negative attitudes of the representatives of the business community towards it are observed during the implementation of the dual model, thus a number of problems arise and become more urgent. I believe that the problem statement itself is a mistake. The effectiveness of the dual model for industrial enterprises is slightly overestimated. In this case, providing the enterprise with quality personnel is the main argument. Companies need qualified personnel, of course, but this problem can be solved with a non-dual model. It would be a big mistake to look at a technologically equipped modern industrial enterprise as a financial sponsor (sponsor) who takes over all costs, including the payment of scholarships. True, it can be said that it is theoretically correct, relying on the dual models that are successfully operating in the Krasnodar region and the city of Krasnodar. However, there are unfortunately not many examples of this generously organized educational process and are aimed at covering a limited number of students. As a rule, it will be the personnel reserve of the partner enterprise selected according to its criteria. The number of this personnel reserve is very small. When the students trained in the dual model are considered in a wider spectrum, it becomes clear that the main contingent of graduates cannot get a job in a dual enterprise, therefore, it makes no sense to talk about the enterprise's interest in them. The introduction of the dual model will be effective and appropriate only if the contingent of students is large. This is the case both from the point of view of the profitability of the dual education process, and from the point of view of its suitability for the educational sector and the labor market as a whole. It is here that it will be possible to assume and confirm that the labor market is annually filled with an army of young, qualified, capable specialists who have both production experience and social production experience. In the dual education model under discussion, it is necessary to emphasize the material interest of the parties within the dual system. On the one hand, there is an educational organization that performs its activities within the framework of the current legislation regulating educational activities in accordance with the tasks specified in the charter. The training organization is in completely different, more complex conditions, it emerges as an intersectoral entity in the dual model.

An important factor that forms the negative attitude of the enterprise towards participation in the dual education system is, on the one hand, the need to provide financial support for this activity, and on the other hand, the diversity of legal documents regulating educational activities, the need to obtain a permit (license) for the implementation of educational activities, to fulfill a number of license conditions and necessity is a particularly important problem, these conditions at first glance seem illogical, and often absurd, for a training enterprise. The process of state accreditation of a laborious educational organization does not exclude the participants of the dual model.

There is no need for licensing, and it can be assumed that there are loopholes in the legislation in this regard, which can be justified by the fact that a specific production enterprise cannot issue a final document on education alone, or it can be based on other grounds. However, in education and business, such a light-hearted approach to legislation is absolutely unacceptable. In this regard, I cite, for example, the current Russian legislation, namely the Federal Law No. 99-FQ of May 4, 2011 "On Licensing of Certain Activities" [1], the Federal Law of December 29, 2012 No. 273-FQ "On Education in the Russian Federation" (I consider it necessary to mention the Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation dated October 28, 2013 N 966 "On Licensing of Educational Activities" (amended on November 29, 2018) [2].

The main requirements for a licensee in the implementation of educational activities are listed in Clause 6 of the Rules on Licensing of Educational Activities, approved by Resolution No. 966 of the Government of the Russian Federation dated October 28, 2013.

Additional license requirements imposed on the licensee in the implementation of educational activities

For the implementation of certain types of educational programs, the licensee is subject to additional license requirements in addition to the above-mentioned basic license requirements (Clause 7 of the Rules):

- the existence of conditions for the operation of an electronic information-educational environment, which includes a set of electronic information resources, electronic educational resources, information technologies, telecommunication technologies and suitable technological tools and ensures full mastery of educational programs by students, regardless of their location, "in the Russian Federation on education" in accordance with Article 16 of the Federal Law, for educational programs where only electronic learning is used - the presence of distance learning technologies;

- In accordance with Part 4 of Article 81 of the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation", as well as in accordance with Article 27 of the Law of the Russian Federation "On State Secrets", information that is considered a state secret for educational purposes, secret weapons, military equipment and existence of a document confirming the permission to use samples of special equipment, their components, special materials and substances;

- for medical education and pharmaceutical education programs in accordance with part 4 of Article 82 of the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" - the presence of conditions that ensure their participation in medical or pharmaceutical activities for the practical training of students;

- In accordance with Article 15 of the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" on the network form of implementation of educational programs between organizations that implement educational activities using the network form of implementation of educational programs, as well as jointly developed and approved by organizations that implement educational activities, educational programs the existence of a contract;

The above non-exhaustive list of license conditions that must be met for the implementation of educational activities in production is not supported by the owners and contributors of the enterprise. Compliance with licensing requirements poses a problem for top managers of enterprises. Either to refuse to invest in a dual education project, or to fulfill the license requirements, it is necessary to look for large financial resources, in which it is often necessary to turn to credit organizations [4]. The management of the partner enterprise does not

like to increase the number of employees who are not engaged in production in the staffing table. This makes it difficult to attract investments in the dual education project. The enterprise, working in the modern fairly unstable economic system, takes on sufficiently large production risks associated with the main production activity. Taking additional risks by investing in educational activity, which is essentially a new type of business activity, will not be profitable for the enterprise and is considered nonsense.

The interest of the owners of industrial enterprises in the implementation of the dual model can be achieved only with the principles of expanding their business activities. Here, it is appropriate for business planning to look at the dual model as diversification of the enterprise's commercial activities with planned concrete financial results and set deadlines. The terms of the business project implementation should take into account the terms of teaching students at the undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate levels. In planning the dual model, it is an important positive factor for the educational organization to know in advance the control numbers for the admissions to the various directions that are implemented in the dual width. It is also important to know in advance the sections of the main educational programs that will be implemented within the framework of the model, which will allow its participants to implement concrete business planning and evaluate the expected financial results of their new educational activities.

The dual model that unites the educational organization and the industrial enterprise should carry out its activities in the direction of one goal - this is a joint, planned profit. Moreover, it is the sole purpose of any business activity, which does not exclude the field of education, and at the same time, it is the main factor or the main motivation for building long-term mutually beneficial cooperation based on clear, transparent market relations.

A number of economic freedoms shared by the modern enterprise with its subordinates are, of course, defined by the principles of the market economy. It is necessary to take them into account when building a dual education model.

Free choice of types and forms of activity . This is the main principle of the market economy. It declares the right of any economic entity to choose the type of economic activity that is desirable, appropriate, useful or preferred and to carry out this activity in any form permitted by law. And here, not only the organizational and legal form of the enterprise, but also the declaration of the type of profitable economic activity of the partner enterprise in the dual education model is considered an important criterion. Dual partnership should be built only in terms of the financial interest of all participants , aiming at the benefit of both parties, which will be possible, first of all, in the joint implementation of non-budget training forms. This practically ensures the possibility of attracting financial resources from the first day of project implementation. A more complex model of integrating dual education into the educational environment is budget education forms, which need further research [6].

Free pricing. In the case of free formation of prices, the price is not limited from the outside, it is not determined by anyone - it is formed as a result of the interaction of supply and demand. Such prices are called free market prices. Thus, participation in the dual model should provide the enterprise and the educational organization with the additional benefit of diversifying its economic activities in the current market at real market prices. When this is followed, according to the essence of the main principle, the participation of the enterprise in the construction of the dual model will now have an understandable and economically based meaning.

Competition is the competition of the subjects of the market relationship to acquire more consumers in order to get more profit from the sale of quality practical-oriented educational products. The principles of competitive struggle should be extended to the quality of the production environment and the quality of the educational environment, both by the educational organization and by the partner enterprise, when considering applicants for the creation of the considered model. Any party can act as the initiator of a dual partnership, and the choice of a partner should be made based on a number of competitive advantages[5].

Equality of market entities with different forms of ownership. This principle means that the economic rights of each subject of the dual model, as well as opportunities for economic activity, restrictions, taxes, benefits should be understandable and compatible. Different forms of ownership create different economic opportunities. This is reflected in taxation issues for commercial enterprises and public educational institutions. In this case, they have different conditions of profit and selection of suppliers and service providers. I believe that the need to conduct various tender procedures for some participants of the model and the absence of such a need for some other participants of the model may cause changes to the contractual relations of the participants of the given educational model, as well as operational changes and additions during the implementation of cooperative activities. These factors should ensure the balance of the distribution of costs for the implementation of the project and should be reflected in the distribution of profits between the partners.

Self-management of economic activity. Self-management of the market economy is primarily ensured by the fact that the decisive role in management is given to economic methods, not administrative-distributive methods. This applies to each participant of the dual model. The market mechanism ensures self-development of the dual model, correction of economic processes by means of competition, bankruptcy and unemployment.

The principle of contractual relations. Market economy is not an economy of orders, but an economy of contracts and agreements. These are instruments for managing economic and contractual relations between the subjects of the dual model and representatives of the external environment - consumers, customers, intermediaries. This principle ensures economic independence, facilitates the transition of relations between partners from mandatory to voluntary, ensures non-dependence on each other in conditions where all parties are obliged to comply with them, and, most importantly, financial independence from each other[5].

Self-sufficiency. Dual model participants are economic entities that are not dependent on each other and have economic independence. Each of them carries out the activities specified in its Charter and covers the financial costs incurred for its operation and development from its own pocket. This principle is very important and calls for living on one's own funds, which forms economic responsibility, money making, control and planning skills. Self-sufficiency of participants of the dual model is part of the general principle - self-sufficiency of economic entities with all necessary resources. Building relationships in terms of self-sufficiency is not a simple but necessary process. It is a process that is especially necessary in situations where partners have different forms of ownership [7].

Economic responsibility. The responsibility of the parties of the dual model arises from the need for the perpetrators to compensate (cover) the damage caused. It is conditioned by the need to comply with the terms of the contract, the violation of these terms is punished by the payment

of large fines, compensations, bonuses, that is, the parties of the dual model, including the students, respond with their own funds, nothing can form the responsibility for fear of losing their money..

The principle of totality of the market - it is impossible to avoid establishing market relations within the proposed model, otherwise the dual model will not be able to work. The model works only if the commodity-money relationship between the participants of the model is a priority. This is the essence of the principle of generality. The need to pay for the use of all rendered services, consumed resources, material base, means of production, natural resources, funds, labor and labor force, intellectual and informational products gives financial independence to partners, and therefore, financial stability .

To be concluded , in the implementation of the basic principles of the market economy, the dual interaction model is useful for industrial enterprises of practically any sector and with different forms of ownership, and creates an attractive investment environment, which allows its participants to invest in a modern and necessary educational model. gives good reason to believe that it will pay dividends. The dual model ensures that modern business is integrated into the educational breadth of society on an equal footing.

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